

DEVELOPMENT OF A SAMARA-INSPIRED AUTOROTATION SYSTEM FOR THE TARGETED DISTRIBUTION OF SENSOR- AND COMMUNICATION NETWORKS ON EARTH AND MARS

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Brief Author Biography: Julian Mutter is a master's student of Aerospace Computer Science at the University of Würzburg. He is currently part of VaMEx3-MarsSymphony, where he is working on development and simulation of autorotation systems.

Introduction: Natural systems often inspire engineering innovations, particularly in aerial mobility. One such example is the Samara seed, which descends with a stable autorotational motion. This work presents the development of a Samara-inspired autorotation system which is capable of controlling its flight and reaching a pre-selected target location. Once at the location, it can land in an upright position, as depicted in Figure 1, using a ground-penetrating spike attached to its frame. This mechanism assures stability, keeping the system in an upright position, which increases the effectiveness of the onboard communications system by increasing the distance of the antenna to the ground. Once successfully landed, payloads like communication beacons or environmental sensors can be operated. Using multiple of these autorotation systems, sensor- and communication networks can be distributed on the surface of planetary bodies. As part of the VaMEx3-MarsSymphony project, this work focuses on the development of the autorotation systems for usage in future Mars missions and demonstrates their operations in various tests on Earth.

Figure 1. The autorotation system in upright landing position on Mars.

Related Work: There exists research exploring the possibility of autorotation experiments on Mars [2]. Also, the aerodynamic properties of Samara-inspired devices and methods for controlling their flight have been investigated [4], [1]. Further, the upright landing using ground-penetration has been shown to be feasible [3]. However, these works were focused on the flight and landing of the autorotation systems and not on the deployment and operation of sensor- and communication payloads. Our work extends upon these findings by not only addressing controlled descent and targeted landing, but also showcasing the simultaneous deployment and operation of payloads carried by multiple autorotation systems.

Prototype development and testing: To date, a prototype of an autorotation system, which is shown in Figure 2, has been developed. The device features a lightweight

frame with an asymmetric blade, optimized for stable descent. It is fitted with a variety of sensors capable of determining the flight path and a communications unit sending this measurement data to a ground station in real time. A battery provides the energy for over 1.5 hours of operation. Further, a servo-motor is integrated to provide active control capabilities. However, at this stage, no control logic has been implemented yet. This will be implemented further down the line during the project run time. Flight tests confirmed that the system successfully achieves passive autorotation, validating its aerodynamic design.

Figure 2. The current prototype of a Samara-inspired autorotation system.

Conclusion & Future Work: The developed prototype successfully demonstrates passive autorotation inspired by Samara seeds. Future iterations of the autorotation system will incorporate a spike for ground-penetration at upright landing. To extend the possible operations duration of the autorotation systems, the integration of solar cells on the wing is also possible. Further, control algorithms for controlled descent and thus targeted sensor deployment will be developed. For this development and the optimization of the control algorithms, a computational simulation of the device's flight dynamics will be created. This simulation will be able to compare control algorithms and wing design for autorotation systems in Earth and Mars environments, allowing investigations of the design not only for Earth but also Mars. Finally, the ability of the autorotation systems to deploy sensor- and communication networks will be verified. To this end, multiple autorotation systems will be deployed and operated simultaneously as part of the VaMEx3-MarsSymphony project.

References:

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